

Why Arrangements and their Maximization in Statistical Mechanics?

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Statistical mechanics texts and also information theory emphasize the use of arrangements (usually using factorials). For example, the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB), Fermi-Dirac (FD) and Bose-Einstein (BE) are often derived from factorial schemes (1) and in information theory, the number of arrangements is a key computation. For example, for a binary alphabet consisting of 0s and 1s, an entropy function equivalent to that of the Fermi-Dirac case is obtained. In a number of notes, we argued one may use reaction balancing to obtain equilibrium distributions, but also showed this could be mapped into arrangements because particles with different energies must be “next to each other” to collide. We also showed that for generalized cases like FD and BE, one may obtain an independent scattering object $g(f(e))$, where $f(e)$ is the number of particles with energy e , such that $g(f(e)) = \exp(-(e-u)/T)$. (2)

In the case of Maxwell-Boltzmann statistics, it is often argued in texts that the number of configurations or positional arrangements is key and is linked to the entropy. We have argued in previous notes that it is the activity in a system which is key. For the MB case, $f(e)$ is the number of particles, but also the probability for a particle with $f(e)$ to collide so for this special case, one may argue either arrangements or activity. For FD and BE cases, we argue that activity is key, although physical arrangements are linked to this activity. For example, for the FD case, a state may have 1 or 0 particles (which is a configurational statement), but it is directly linked to whether scattering into this state may occur or not. For the BE case, one may have $f(e)$ bosons with energy e , but for scattering considerations, it is the number of bosons in the same location in space (or in a degenerate box located at a specific position) which enhances the scattering probability into that same degenerate box.

The purpose of this note is to try to examine why arrangements are used in statistical mechanics, how they link to activity and why they are maximized, especially given that one may obtain the equilibrium distribution $f(e)$ using reaction balance which uses “averaging”, but does not directly use any arrangement or factorial schemes.

Reaction Balance

One may obtain equilibrium distributions without any need for factorial schemes, entropy or partition functions. One simply balances all possible reactions and their time reversed scenarios. In some cases, however, “averaging” is needed, such as in the FD case, because a fermion is either in a state or not, but one uses $f(e)$ which is neither 0 or 1. For the MB case,

$f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ ((1a)) and $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ ((1b)) Taking \ln of ((1a)) and associating with ((1b)) yields: $f(e) = \exp(-(e-u)/T)$ ((1c))

In more general cases, we argue that ((1a)) is replaced with: $g(e_1)g(e_2) = g(e_3)g(e_4)$ ((2a)) and ((1c)) becomes: $g(e) = \exp(-(e-u)/T)$. This is in keeping with results of Kaniadakis, although he uses a Fokker Planck equation and not reaction balance (3).

At this point, one may wonder why one would use a factorial counting scheme at all, yet statistical mechanics texts and information theory seem to use such schemes as fundamental starting points and in the case of statistical mechanics, maximization of entropy subject to constraints is also applied.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Case

In (4), we mapped the MB case into arrangements. For a reaction to occur, a particle with energy e_1 must be next to a particle with e_2 , otherwise they will not collide. Thus, it seems there might be a reason to map particles in three-space into a line (using some kind of scheme) and argue that if e_1 and e_2 are next to each other (on the line), they will interact.

For a system with M particles with m_1 having energy e_1 , m_2 energy e_2 etc, one has the following number of arrangements:

$$M! / (m_1! m_2! \dots) \quad ((3))$$

By looking at the different arrangements, one may pick out all e_1 - e_2 pairs and e_3 - e_4 pairs and switch e_1 - e_2 into e_3 - e_4 . This can also be done for all pairs which conserve energy i.e. $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. If the number of arrangements remains unchanged, then one has, it seems, an equilibrium situation because this is equivalent to reaction balance. Thus, there is a special case of m_i values which gives a number of arrangements which map directly into an equilibrium scenario. The probability to have an e_1 next to e_2 is: $f(e_1)f(e_2)$ and for an e_3 - e_4 pair: $f(e_3)f(e_4)$. This holds for all pairs with energy= e_1+e_2 . Thus, it seems that $f(e_1)=\exp(-(e-u)/T)$ is a solution for m_1 at equilibrium. This still does not prove that the number of arrangements has been maximized.

A hand-wavy argument indicating that the number of arrangements is maximized is the following. Consider two sets of m_i values $m(1)_i$ and $m(2)_i$ and let $m(1)_i$ have fewer arrangements than $m(2)_i$. The arrangements not only measure the number of positional configurations, but they indicate activity, because the system changes from one arrangement to another. Thus, more arrangements imply more activity. Thus, a system with more arrangements, in this case $m(2)_i$, has more physical configurations and activity and there is no physical reason for these to be restricted at equilibrium. Thus, it seems one would choose the maximum number of arrangements as representing equilibrium. It is already known that $f(e_1)=\exp(-(e-u)/T)$ yields an equilibrium solution. Thus, in order to maximize the number of arrangements, one may maximize $S(f(e_i)=m_i)$ related to the number of arrangements subject to the constraint $(e-u)/T f(e_i)$. Thus, $d/df S(f) = -(e-u)/T$ for maximization. From ((3)) $S = \text{Sum over } i -f(e_i) \ln(f(e_i))$ if one uses Stirling's approximation, thus $d/df S$ does in fact equal $-(e-u)/T$ and one is extremizing the number of arrangements.

Fermi-Dirac Case?

What should be done in the Fermi-Dirac case? From reaction balance one has:

$g(f) = \exp(-(e-u)/T) = f/(1-f)$ ((4)) because ((1a)) is replaced with:

$$f(e_1)[1-f(e_3)]f(e_2)[1-f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1-f(e_1)]f(e_4)[1-f(e_2)] \quad ((5))$$

((5)) may be rearranged such that $g(f) = f/(1-f)$ is an independent mathematical object. One may then map this mathematical object (related to scattering activity) to the arrangements as done in the previous section for the MB case.

In textbooks and information theory, however, this is not done. Arrangement mapping is done directly into energy levels as this is the physical scenario. It is argued that if $f(e_i)$ is the average number of fermions in level e , then if there are g_i degenerate boxes, one may arrange the fermions in:

$$g_i! / [f(e_i)! (1-f(e_i))!] \text{ ways} \quad ((6)) \quad (\text{see (1) p 183})$$

If one does not like the g_i degenerate boxes (there is no degeneracy for a 1-D Fermi gas), one might think of each box as a slice in time i.e. dt . ((6)) is the number of arrangements of the fermion in level e_1 in time, but why is that important? ((4)) shows that one maximizes activity given by $g(f)$. It has already been argued in the MB section that $g(f) = \exp(-(e-u)/T)$ represents a maximum number of arrangements. If $g(f)$ is mapped into the physical scenarios in time for a fermion to occupy state e_i , this number of arrangements should also be maximized to match $g(f)$. To do so, one maximizes ((6)) subject to the constraint $f(e_i) = \exp(-(e-u)/T)$. This yields the Fermi-Dirac solution. Using ((4)), one may then find $g(f)$.

It should be noted here that one has an extra constraint (beyond total particle number and total energy) that affects activity or scattering. That constraint is the rule that a particle cannot scatter into e_i if there is already a particle there. The number of configurations in time is definitely not a configuration arrangement (it is in time), but it is again linked to the kind of activity occurring i.e. during time slice 1 the fermion is in e_1 , then it may move out in time t_2 then in in time 3 etc. The various arrangements are linked to activity scenarios.

For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $f(e)$ and $g(f)$ are the same, i.e. $g = \text{the identity function}$ and there is no extra constraint related to scattering.

Fermi-Dirac Case and Information Theory

In information theory, one often sees the example of a message created, with each letter x_i having a probability of $p(x_i)$ of occurring. If the alphabet has two letters, one may call one 0 and the other 1. This is a binary code alphabet and is considered in (5) with the arrangements being:

$$N! / [(Np)! (N-Np)!] \quad \text{where } N \text{ is large and } p \text{ is the probability for a "1"}$$

This is exactly the number of arrangements used in the Fermi-Dirac case and leads to an information entropy (using Stirling's formula) which is the same as that for fermions. In

information theory “In base 2” is used in this case, while \ln base e is used in statistical mechanics. The number of arrangements in information theory is given here as 2 to the power of entropy, where entropy represents the length of “message” i.e. an originally N long message has been compacted down to NS where S is entropy = $-p \log(2) p - (1-p) \log(2) (1-p)$.

Bose-Einstein Case for Bosons

Like fermions, bosons carry an extra constraint related to scattering. If $f(e)$ bosons exist in a state (at a location) and another boson wants to scatter into this same state, scattering is enhanced by a factor of $f(e)+1$ (6). Thus, $g(f)=f/(1+f)$ because:

$$f(e_1) [1+f(e_3)] f(e_2)[1+f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1+f(e_1)] f(e_4)[1+f(e_2)] \quad ((8))$$

A question arises as to why one would need a special arrangement to describe the boson scenario. The reason, it seems, is that scattering is enhanced due to the boson $f(e)+1$ factor. Thus, this is not Maxwell-Boltzmann scattering where probability is: $f(e_1)f(e_2)$. The enhancement, however, only occurs if n bosons are together in the same location of space. $f(e)$ represents the number of bosons with energy e , but they are not necessarily altogether in the same “degenerate box”. Imagine that there are $f(e_i)$ bosons with energy e_i and g_i degenerate boxes. The number of bosons in a box plus 1 represents the enhancement of scattering into that particular box. The number of arrangements is given in (1) as:

$$(f(e_i)+g_i-1)! / [f(e_i)! (g_i-1)!] \quad ((9))$$

This is obtained by considering the total number of permutations of $f(e_i)$ balls and g_i-1 inner walls. (Imagine there are two fixed outer walls.) This set of physical arrangements related to the scattering constraint should be maximized to match $g(f)=\exp(-(e-u)/T)$.

Note: One maximizes the number of groupings of bosons as all of these are physically possible and there is no constraint to prevent any arrangement. One does not maximize the probability for one particular type of reaction to occur i.e. place all of the $f(e)$ bosons in one degenerate box.

Maximizing ((9)) by varying f subject to the constraint $(e-u)/T f(e_i)$ yields the Bose-Einstein distribution which may be used to obtain $g(f)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that for generalized scattering, one may create a function $g(f)$ which behaves as an independent scattering probability and for reaction balance i.e. equilibrium is equal to $\exp(-(e-u)/T)$. For the MB case, $g(f)=f$. We also argue that one may map this reaction balance into a set of arrangements given by $M! / (m_1! M_2! \dots)$ where m_i =the number of particles with energy e_i . The equilibrium solution is one which maximizes the set of arrangements, although reaction balance yields the equilibrium solution with no arrangements (given by factorials) and no maximization necessary.

Because g is not f as it is in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, we argue that there are often extra constraints related to scattering. For fermions, only one fermion can be in level e_i (ignoring spin). For bosons, the number with energy e_i in a specific physical location enhances scattering of another boson into e_i in that same physical location (by a factor of $n+1$ where n is the number of bosons in the location). We argue that these two restrictions may be mapped into arrangements. For the FD case, one takes time slices. There is a probability of $f(e_i)$ for the fermion to be in level e_i so one uses $g_i! / [f(e_i)! (g_i - f(e_i))!]$ to find the number of arrangements in time. For bosons, one has $f(e_i)$ in level e_i , but not all are the same physical location. One imagines g_i degenerate boxes in different physical locations and finds the number of arrangements into these. Because one knows that $g(f)$ for both the FD and BE cases is a maximum, one maximizes the scattering restriction/enhancement specific arrangements subject to the constraint $(e_i - u)/T f(e_i)$ to obtain an $f(e_i)$ which maps to $g(f)$. Thus, we argue that it is activity or scattering issues which ultimately govern a statistical system, but that these may, as in the case of fermions or bosons, be mapped into arrangements, either in time or location which are directly linked to the restriction/enhancement involved.

In the case of fermions, one may argue that one may have only one fermion in a level. In the case of boson, one has no such restriction. Why should one consider g_i degenerate boxes for e_i ? It seems that this is due to the scattering (activity) rule that only the number of bosons with energy e_i in a specific location enhance scattering of another boson into that location.

Thus, $g(f)$ is a maximum and one creates a set of arrangements related to scattering restrictions/enhancements and maximizes that so that it maps into $g(f)$. For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, there are no "additional" restrictions/enhancements and this is not necessary. $g(f)=f$ in the MB case.

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